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**LABOR MIGRATION AND ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL FACTORS
AFFECTING IT**

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Abstract: This article analyses the official and unofficial forms of labor migration, their seasonal, temporary and repetitive characteristics, as well as the influence of economic, social and demographic factors affecting migration by the example of some regions of the republic.

Keywords. Labor market, labor migration, donor and recipient countries, foreign labor migrants, high wages.

INTRODUCTION

Labor migration refers to the territorial migration of the population within and beyond the borders of the country for different periods of time in order to sell the knowledge, skills and abilities of migrants in the labor market. In world practice, the following factors cause labor migration: economic inequality between rich and poor countries; demographic imbalance of the population; damage to social relations as a result of economic development; relations between donor and recipient countries; cheap labor of migrants and others. The causes of labor migration in the Republic of Uzbekistan, especially in the southwestern regions of the republic, are as follows: insufficient jobs; low cost of labor; lack of a permanent job with a high salary;

relatively low living conditions; earning money for studying; insufficient work in the specialty; not having any profession or trade, etc.

The main part. For developed countries, migrants help to provide cheap labor force, to fill fields lacking highly qualified specialists with educated people [1; p. 14]. The existence of the above problems in providing employment to the population in the labor market requires effective organization of labor migration. In the current period, the main factors of economic, socio-demographic and organizational-legal characteristics have a direct impact on the change of foreign labor migration. The main economic factors of foreign labor migration include higher opportunities for work and higher income, establishment of a special fund for training citizens for professions and supporting them in migration abroad, giving tax incentives to agencies providing services in the field of employment.

The introduction of the amount of wages paid to migrants sufficient to the minimum consumption basket, the ease of doing business, the availability of technical opportunities for industrial innovation or new industries, allowing labor migrants to receive loans from commercial banks for transportation and other expenses, and international distribution of loans, convenient mechanisms for receiving and paying through payment systems have a significant impact.

Statistical data and their analysis. Improving the qualifications of the labor force as a socio-demographic factor, collecting information from foreign employers of the labor exporting country about job vacancies, nature of work, salary, qualifications (skills) required of workers, providing necessary medical care and good hygienic conditions. Also, it is important for the employer to take care of health insurance for the migrants he offers to work, to provide them with beds and to ensure that they comply with sanitary and hygienic standards.

Table 1

Changes in the number of foreign labor migrants in South-western Uzbekistan, thousand people

The table was compiled based on the information of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan

According to the data of the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations, the share of foreign labor migrants in southwestern Uzbekistan is 37.8 percent, and their number has increased by 5.89 times in 2010-2020 (Table 1). In 2020, 673 citizens of southwestern Uzbekistan were sent abroad to work in an organized manner by the Agency for Foreign Labor Migration. In particular, according to the bilateral agreement, 614 citizens of Uzbekistan were sent to work in the Republic of Korea, 50 labor migrants were sent to Russia, and 9 citizens were sent to work in Bulgaria. As can be seen from the table, during the analyzed period, the number of foreign labor migrants grew faster in Kashkadarya (7.64 times) and Surkhandarya (7.52 times) regions than in other regions. Such a situation requires paying more serious attention to the issues of foreign labor migration at the state level, and constantly improving the existing mechanisms for its regulation. 80.7% of citizens working abroad (2020) are men, and the remaining 19.3% are women. More than half (56.8 percent) of foreign labor migrants are young people. When analyzed by country, 61.5% of foreign labor migrants live in the Russian Federation, 12.1% - in the Republic of Kazakhstan, 9.5% - in Turkey, 5.3% - in the Republic of Korea, 1.2% - in the United Arab Emirates, the rest 10.3 percent work in other countries (Table 2). The analysis of the regions of South-Western Uzbekistan shows that the percentage of people who go to work from the Bukhara region to the Russian Federation, from the Navoi region to Kazakhstan and the Republic of Korea, from the Samarkand region to Turkey and the United Arab Emirates is more than in other regions of the region. Labor migration has formal and informal forms. Official labor migration has been established in Uzbekistan with the Republic of Korea, the Russian Federation, Turkey, the UAE, Bulgaria, Poland, and Japan. In the research period (2010-2020), the number of people employed abroad by agency decreased from 2,085 to 673 or 67.8 percent.

Table 2. Changes in the number of people employed abroad through the external labor migration agency from the population of South-western regions of Uzbekistan, people

№	The name of regions	2010 y			2016 y			2018 y			2019 y					2020 y					
		Total	from this:		Total	from this:		Total	from this:			Total	from this:				Total	from this:			
			Korea	Russia		Korea	Russia		Korea	Russia	Japan		Korea	Russia	Turkey	Poland		Bulgaria	Korea	Russia	Bulgaria
1	Bukhara	317	52	265	95	92	3	115	44	71	-	198	56	112	30	-	-	191	170	21	-
2	Kashkadarya	723	199	524	392	387	5	433	373	59	1	397	349	41	7	-	-	277	243	25	9
3	Navoi	210	210	-	72	72	-	89	57	32	-	133	70	56	7	-	-	50	49	1	-
4	Samarkand	749	749	-	172	172	-	376	331	43	2	315	220	83	12	-	-	40	40	-	-
5	Surkhandarya	86	86	-	67	67	-	139	63	72	4	98	56	34	8	-	-	115	112	3	-
	Total	2085	1296	789	798	790	8	1152	868	277	7	1141	751	326	64	-	-	673	614	50	9

The table is compiled based on the information of the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Such a decreasing trend was also observed in Bukhara, Kashkadarya, Navoi and Samarkand regions of the region. In particular, in 2020, the number of official foreign migrants decreased by 94.7% in Samarkand region, 76.2% in Navoi region, 61.7% in Kashkadarya region, and 39.8% in Bukhara region compared to 2010. During the research period, the number of people employed abroad through the agency increased only in Surkhandarya region of the region (from 86 to 115 people, respectively). It is worth noting that during 2010-2017, citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan were sent to work in only 2 countries - Korea and Russia, and since 2018, the geography of

official labor migration has expanded. That is, the countries of Japan, Turkey, Poland and Bulgaria have also joined. Through private employment agencies, in 2019, 1,227 citizens of southwestern Uzbekistan were employed abroad. According to statistics, they were employed in 22 countries by private employment agencies. Most of the foreign labor migrants were sent to Russia, Turkey, Lithuania, Latvia, Poland and Bulgaria. When analyzed by regions, the largest number of foreign labor migrants were sent from Bukhara, Surkhandarya and Kashkadarya regions.

Labor migration in the republic differs in that it has a more informal appearance. This situation is reflected in the seasonal, temporary and recurring nature of this type of labor migration. The action performed without the issue of a work visa, permit, employment contract, special card for migrants, customs declaration and similar official documents has an unofficial status. Under the influence of the above-mentioned factors, the population is provided with work in various fields and industries in different districts and cities. Based on the information of the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations, the regions of the republic can be divided into 3 groups according to the availability of labor resources [18]:

Regions rich in labor resources are Samarkand, Fergana, Kashkadarya, Andijan, Namangan, Tashkent and Surkhandarya regions. Regions moderately provided with labor resources are the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Bukhara and Khorezm regions. Regions with insufficient labor resources are Jizzakh, Syrdarya and Navoi regions. It can be seen that the regions of Samarkand, Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya in the south-west of Uzbekistan are richly supplied with labor resources, Bukhara region is moderately supplied, and Navoi region is among the poorly supplied regions. Organized and effective internal migration of people from regions with abundant labor resources to regions with less resources ensures equal distribution of labor resources of the republic. It is manifested in the directions of labor migrants within the republic from villages to cities, from district centers to other large cities, or from one region to another.

Internal labor migration in south-western Uzbekistan is equal to 8.9%. Large cities play a role in internal labor migration. In particular, 70.0-80.0 percent of internal migration of the republic corresponds to the city of Tashkent. Rural-urban migration has a positive significance in the republic. After all, the majority of the population lives in the rural areas of the country, and the population continues to grow at a high rate in these areas. In these densely populated areas, the labor force is more than needed, despite the fact that the creation of new jobs in rural areas of the country is of the first priority, the problem of providing employment to labor resources remains acute.

Labor migration in the south-western region of Uzbekistan is mainly characterized by seasonality and repetition, and the majority of this type of labor movement is accounted for by rural residents (80.5%). One of the main reasons for this is the increase in the supply of labor force and the relatively low availability of employment in rural areas.

Table 3. Changes in the number of internal labor migrants in southwestern Uzbekistan, thousand people

The name of regions	2010 y	2015 y	2016 y	2017 y	2018 y	2019 y	2020 y	2020-yilda 2010-yilga nisbatan (%)
Bukhara	4,6	4,9	5,2	5,4	4,9	5,4	5,8	126,1
Kashkadarya	7,2	8,1	9,3	8,9	8,8	9,6	10,3	143,1
Navoi	8,6	9,1	9,4	10,4	10,5	9,1	9,9	115,1
Samarkand	8,3	9,9	8,6	8,3	9,6	9,4	10,6	127,7
Surkhandarya	7,8	9,3	9,4	11,6	9,6	10,3	11,8	151,3
Total	36,9	41,3	41,9	44,6	43,4	43,8	48,4	131,2

The table is compiled based on the information of the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The main reason for the emergence of seasonal labor migration in the republic is that a large part of the labor force is mobilized mainly for agriculture in rural areas and the temporary, i.e., seasonal nature of work in this sector. According to the information

of the Ministry, internal labor migration of working-age population is becoming active in the studied region (Table 2). Among the regions of the areas, the regions with active internal migration are mainly observed in Surkhondarya, Kashkadarya, Samarkand and Bukhara regions. Over the past 2010-2020, internal migration has increased in Sukhondarya (151.3 percent), Kashkadarya (143.1 percent), Samarkand (217.7 percent), and Bukhara region (126.1 percent). It can be seen that the lowest indicator belongs to Navoi region (115.1 percent) (Table 2).

Three important directions of movement of labor migrants within the republic can be highlighted:

Tashkent is the first city and the main route for all regions of the republic.

The second direction is within the regions, where regional centers play an important role.

The third direction is the centers of regional districts. As mentioned above, the majority of this type of labor movement is accounted for by rural residents (80.5%). The main reasons why the main part of the internal labor movement is accounted for by rural residents are explained by the following:

First, the presence of surplus labor resources in the rural areas of the region's regions.

Secondly, there is a lack of jobs and low employment opportunities in rural areas.

Thirdly, the migration of labor migrants to regional centers or the capital is explained by the large number of seasonal jobs and relatively high wages.

Labor force of the Republic of Uzbekistan to foreign countries due to export:

- to the national income of the republic due to labor force export.

Funds are added from abroad.

- migrants bring with them the most up-to-date knowledge, foreign experiences that are important for production and study the effective use of modern technologies;
- organization of existing labor in foreign companies and enterprises

- to work efficiently, to learn how to properly manage the production process, and most importantly, to acquire modern knowledge and skills.

There are positive and negative aspects of labor export. In our opinion, it is appropriate to implement the following in order to regulate migration in the regions and to properly use labor migrants:

Table 4. Advantages and disadvantages of labor export

Positive	Negative
1. Acquisition of new professional skills by workers	1. Loss of skilled labor
2. Reduction of the balance of payments deficit	2. Increasing dependence on international demand for labor in addition to goods
3. Balance of demand and supply in the domestic labor market	3. Directing the capital used for the development of production resources intended for consumption to other areas
4. Structural and technological restructuring of production	4. An increase in the rate of inflation

The table is compiled by the author

Firstly, it is necessary to establish the activity of centers dealing with internal labor migration issues in all districts of the republic. It is necessary to organize labor market monitoring in order to develop the balance of mobility of labor resources by region, industry, and occupation of these centers, to identify persons who need to change their place of residence in the regions.

Secondly, the centers will correctly define regional migration routes by dividing the republic's cities and districts into groups according to the extent to which they are provided with labor resources.

Thirdly, to fully ensure the legal and social protection of citizens moving to other regions.

Fourthly, in order to regulate labor migration, it is necessary to create a mechanism for hiring, training qualified workers and specialists in accordance with the

orders of labor importing countries and large employer companies under the leadership of relevant organizations and ministries. Migrants should be taught the language, history, customs, and traditions of the country where they will work, and the necessary qualifications and skills for the chosen work, profession, and craft should be formed.

CONCLUSIONS

It was found that life expectancy at birth in southwestern Uzbekistan is slightly higher than the national average, life expectancy at birth in the republic is 0.4 years, and in the studied area it is 0.1 years longer. It was found that foreign labor migrants have grown at a high rate in south-western Uzbekistan. Such a situation requires paying more serious attention to the issues of foreign labor migration at the state level, and constantly improving the existing mechanisms for its regulation.

In order to regulate migration in the regions and properly use labor migrants, it is proposed to establish centers dealing with internal and external labor migration issues in all districts of the republic. These centers carry out such important tasks as developing the balance of labor resources’ regional, branch, and occupational mobility, identifying persons who need to change their place of residence in the regions, and organizing constant control of the labor market.

REFERENCES:

1. ABDURAMANOV, K. K., & IBRAGIMOV, L. Z. (2015). Regional Characteristics Of Demographic Development In The Republic Of Uzbekistan. *SEA-Practical Application of Science*, (7), 363-368.
2. Ibragimov, L., & Muminjonova, S. (2023). Hududlarni iqtisodiy rivojlanishida yer va suv resurslarining ahamiyati. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 3(1 Part 2), 164–169. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.35281/zenodo.7539710>